

ABSTRACT

Studies have shown that stigma affects the implementation, support, and acceptance of policies introduced to mitigate the issues associated with sex work, the oldest profession, in different countries and cultures worldwide. Here we determined the level of social stigma across three living generations of Filipinos and their readiness for the possibility of decriminalizing the oldest profession in the Philippines using research-made survey questionnaires deliberately validated by psychometricians. Respondents across three generations of Filipinos, namely, Generation Z, Millennials, and Generation X, were included in this study. The results showed a high level of social stigma towards sex work across the generations and a high level of readiness toward decriminalizing sex work. However, there is a noticeable difference in the levels of social stigma and readiness among the respondents. Generation X showed the highest level of social stigma towards sex work, while Generation Z showed the lowest level of social stigma. On the readiness towards decriminalizing sex work, Generation Z showed the highest level, while Generation X showed the lowest level among the respondents. Analysis of this data showed no relationship between generational difference and readiness towards decriminalizing sex work. However, mediation analysis resulted in a positive outcome showing that social stigma is a mediator in the relationship between generational difference and readiness towards decriminalizing sex work. This implies that social stigma impacts an individual's readiness of an individual regardless of age or generation. Contrary to the idea that older people could be more resistant to decriminalizing sex work and younger people more open to this idea, this research shows that regardless of age or generation, a person can be ready or not ready to accept this change depending on their level of social stigma associated towards sex work.

Keywords: *Social Stigma, Readiness, Sex Work, Decriminalization, Generational Difference*

INTRODUCTION

According to Merriam-Webster, prostitution is "the world's oldest profession," having the earliest records dating back to 2400 BC in ancient Babylonia (Hager & Schwartz, 2021). Prostitution was defined as engaging, agreeing, or offering to engage in sexual conduct with another person for a fee (Green, 2016). In the Philippines, sex work is referred to as "prostitution" (Roces, 2009). During the 16th Congress of the second regular session, Senator Pia Cayetano (2015) proposed Senate Bill No. 2621, popularly known as the Anti-Prostitution Act of 2015, which aims to address the system of prostitution in the Philippines by imposing penalties on its perpetrators and providing protective measures, support, and services for its victims (the prostituted). This is because the proposal could be that engaging in sex work is considered a criminal offense in Section 1, Article 202 of the Revised Penal Code (Joven, 2020). The Philippines decriminalizes sex work, and various agencies and organizations have different opinions.

The Philippine Commission on Women (2021) agrees that prostitution should be decriminalized, and the government should not arrest and punish prostituted people as criminals. Instead, programs that provide reparation and renewal for an alternative lifestyle and career for them should be implemented. On the other hand, GABRIELA maintains its position that sex work should not be considered because women labeled as prostituted women cannot be recognized as society's average workers (Joven, 2020). Then, the Nordic model is implemented in Nordic countries, which puts sex work in the context of male violence against women (Vuolajärvi, 2019). Sex workers who are not labeled as criminals have easier access to the legal system and are encouraged to report behaviors that endanger themselves and other women in the industry (Forestiery, 2019). The legalization and laws of Sex work in Australia vary depending on the state.

In the Australian Capital Territory, for example, since the adoption of "Anna's Law" in 1992, sex work has been allowed. Readiness, in the APA dictionary of psychology, is a state of preparedness to act or to resist the study aims of this study are to find out how different generations perceive sex work and how they feel about decriminalizing sex work if they are mentally prepared to decriminalize it. Moreover, suppose social stigma has a mediating role in the relationship of generational differences of Filipinos towards their readiness to decriminalize sex work. In that case, we, researchers, believe it will be helpful as a reference medium in future studies with the same scope. This could serve to reduce the stigma attached to sex workers, as well as raise awareness and information about sex work and sex workers in general. Furthermore, this sought to provide information to government

agencies and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to aid in promoting initiatives for the protection and well-being of sex workers. Finally, this will assist the community in alleviating the stigma associated with them and providing knowledge on how the stigma should be handled.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. The research design that was used for this study is descriptive-correlational. Descriptive research is a valuable tool that allows a researcher to collect data and use statistical analysis to characterize the demographics of that data. Likewise, correlational is commonly used to describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. As a result, it is a quantitative research technique. Researchers have used this quantitative research to determine how social stigma is a mediator that affects the perception of generational differences towards sex work and their readiness to decriminalize sex work. The researcher used a survey questionnaire as a research instrument to collect data from the respondents.

Participants/Respondents. The questionnaire was uploaded in Google Forms, and the link was included in the letter to respondents. Upon clicking the link, the respondents were directed to the web page with the informed consent form and the proper questionnaire, which they could answer. Their submitted response was consolidated by Google Forms, where the researchers can access their individual and consolidated answers. One hundred sixty-two respondents from Generation Z, 116 from Millennials, and 81 from Generation X were collected within one month.

Data Collection Procedure. The raw data were carefully reviewed, tallied, and analyzed. The results obtained from the tabulation were treated statistically using the frequency count, weighted mean, linear regression, and multiple linear regression. **Data Analysis Procedure.** Discuss the statistical tools utilized in the study (if any)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Generation and Age of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of 359 respondents in this research regarding generation and age.

Wherein twenty-two-point fifty-six percent (22.56%) belong to Generation X with the age range of 46-57, thirty-two-point thirty-one percent (32.31%) belong to Millennials with the age range of 27-45-, and forty-five-point thirteen percent (45.13%) belong to Generation Z with the age range of 18-26. The most significant number of respondents gathered belong to Generation Z because they have convenient access to online platforms used in the data gathering of the research. The least is Generation Y since they need help accessing the platforms utilized in data gathering, and the researchers only reached out to them through their family members.

Table 1

Generation (Age Range)	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Generation Z (18-26)	162	45.13	1
Millennials (27-45)	116	32.31	2
Generation X (46-57)	81	22.56	3
TOTAL	359	100	

Gender of the Respondents

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of 359 respondents of this research in terms of gender.

Wherein forty-five-point thirteen percent (45.13%) comprise the male respondents, and fifty-four-point eighty-seven percent (54.87%) comprise the female respondents. Female respondents are more accommodating to answering the survey questionnaire online than male respondents, as seen in the number of replies we received upon gathering data.

Table 2

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Male	162	45.13	2
Female	197	54.87	1
TOTAL	359	100	

Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of 359 respondents in this research regarding their highest educational attainment.

Wherein, zero point twenty-eight percent (0.28%) belong to respondents with a Doctorate, one point sixty-seven percent (1.67%) belong to respondents with a Master's degree, two-point twenty-three percent (2.23%) belong to respondents with Vocational courses, four-point eighteen percent (4.18%) belong to respondents that are Elementary level or graduate, sixteen points seventy-one percent (16.71%) belongs to respondents with Bachelor's degree, twenty-five point ninety-one percent (25.91%) belongs to respondents that are High school level or graduate. Forty-nine point zero three percent (49.03%) belongs to respondents that are College level.

The highest number of respondents gathered have College level educational attainment since many of the respondents gathered belong to Generation Z that are currently studying.

Table 3

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Elementary Level/Graduate	15	4.18	4
High School Level/Graduate	93	25.91	2
College Level	176	49.03	1
Bachelor's Degree	60	16.71	3
Master's Degree	6	1.67	6
Doctorate Degree	1	0.28	7
Vocational	8	2.23	5
TOTAL	359	100	

Social Stigma Towards the Oldest Profession Generation Z

Table 4 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Social Stigma Towards the Oldest Profession survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to Generation Z.

The overall weighted mean of the respondents belonging to Generation Z represents their level of social stigma towards the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Generational Z responses yielded a score of thirty-five point thirty (35.30) with an interpretation of a high level of social stigma. This shows that the image portrayed by the mainstream media that sex work is performed either by innocent victims or immoral women is highly observable in Generation Z respondents (Parmanand, 2016).

Table 4

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Bad women do sex work with loose morals.	2.43	Low
2. Most of the people who do sex work are victims of human trafficking.	3.60	High
3. People who do sex work need to be rescued.	4.13	High
4. Sex work is a profession that goes against the morality of society.	3.60	High

5. Sex work is a crime, and sex workers should be punished by law.	3.33	Moderate
6. Authorities should arrest and penalize individuals who do sexwork.	3.19	Moderate
7. It is demoralizing to do sex work.	3.91	High
8. People doing sex work should be pitied.	3.17	Moderate
9. Individuals who do sex work lose their dignity.	3.94	High
10. Sex work wrecks homes and families.	3.98	High
TOTAL	35.30	High

Social Stigma Towards the Oldest Profession Millennials

Table 5 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Social Stigma Towards Sex Work survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to the Millennials.

The overall weighted mean of the respondents belonging to the Millennials represents their level of social stigma toward the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Millennials' responses yielded a score of thirty-seven point twenty-eight (37.28) with an interpretation of a high level of social stigma. This shows that the image portrayed by the mainstream media that sex work is performed either by innocent victims or immoral women is highly observable in the Millennial respondents (Parmanand, 2016).

Table 5

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Sex work is done by bad women with loose morals.	2.91	Moderate
2. Most of the people who do sex work are victims of human trafficking.	3.58	High
3. People who do sex work need to be rescued.	3.91	High
4. Sex work is a profession that goes against the morality of society.	3.70	High
5. Sex work is a crime, and sex workers should be punished by law.	3.80	High
6. Authorities should arrest and penalize individuals who do sexwork.	3.53	High
7. It is demoralizing to do sex work.	4.05	High
8. People doing sex work should be pitied.	3.65	High
9. Individuals who do sex work lose their dignity.	4.03	High
10. Sex work wrecks homes and families.	4.12	High
TOTAL	37.28	High

Social Stigma Towards the Oldest Profession Generation X

Table 6 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Social Stigma Towards Sex Work survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to Generation X.

The overall weighted mean of the respondents belonging to Generation X represents their level of social stigma towards the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Generation X

responses yielded a score of thirty-nine point zero five (39.05) with an interpretation of a High level of social stigma. This shows that the image portrayed by the mainstream media that sex work is performed either by innocent victims or immoral women is highly observable in Generation X respondents (Parmanand, 2016).

Table 6

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Sex work is done by bad women with loose morals.	3.74	High
2. Most of the people who do sex work are victims of humantrafficking.	3.69	High
3. People who do sex work need to be rescued.	3.84	High
4. Sex work is a profession that goes against the morality of society.	3.98	High
5. Sex work is a crime, and sex workers should be punished by law.	3.84	High
6. Authorities should arrest and penalize individuals who do sexwork.	3.85	High
7. It is demoralizing to do sex work.	4.30	High
8. People doing sex work should be pitied.	3.36	High
9. Individuals who do sex work lose their dignity.	4.17	High
10. Sex work wrecks homes and families.	4.28	High
TOTAL	39.05	High

Readiness Towards Decriminalizing the Oldest Profession Generation Z

Table 7 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to Generation Z.

The overall weighted mean of the Generation Z respondents represents their readiness for decriminalizing the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Generation Z responses yielded a score of thirty-six point twenty-one (36.21) with an interpretation of a high level of readiness. This shows that Generation Z respondents are highly inclined toward accepting the policies of the proposed Senate Bill No. 2621 (Cayetano, 2015).

Table 7

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Prostitutes/sex workers should not be considered criminals.	3.36	Moderate
2. The people who patronize sex work should be the ones to be penalized.	3.73	High
3. Establishment owners that perpetuate sex work should be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.90	High
4. Prostitutes/sex workers should be considered victims of crime and not criminals.	3.46	Moderate
5. The person who receives sexual acts by a prostitute/sex worker should be penalized by the	3.72	High

law.		
6. The government should protect and support sex workers instead of being treated as criminals.	3.23	Moderate
7. People who recruit sex workers shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	4.05	High
8. To stop prostitution, we must stop treating sex workers as criminals.	3.49	Moderate
9. People who profit from sex work shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.85	High
10. I am in favor of changing the law that criminalizes sex workers.	3.40	Moderate
TOTAL	36.21	High

Readiness Toward Decriminalizing the Oldest Profession Millennials

Table 8 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to the Millennials.

The overall weighted mean of the respondents belonging to the Millennials represents their level of readiness toward decriminalizing the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Millennial’s responses yielded a score of thirty-six point ten (36.10) with an interpretation of a High level of readiness. This shows that the Millennial respondents have a high inclination toward accepting the policies of the proposed Senate Bill No. 2621 (Cayetano, 2015).

Table 8

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Prostitutes/sex workers should not be considered criminals.	3.47	Moderate
2. The people who patronize sex work should be the ones to be penalized.	3.59	High
3. Establishment owners that perpetuate sex work should be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.77	High
4. Prostitutes/sex workers should be considered victims of crime and not criminals.	3.49	Moderate
5. The person who receives sexual acts by a prostitute/sex worker should be penalized by the law.	3.71	High
6. The government should protect and support sex workers instead of being treated as criminals.	3.29	Moderate
7. People who recruit sex workers shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.93	High
8. To stop prostitution, we must stop treating sex workers as criminals.	3.44	Moderate
9. People who profit from sex work shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.79	High
10. I am in favor of changing the law that criminalizes sex workers.	3.62	High
TOTAL	36.10	High

Readiness Towards Decriminalizing the Oldest Profession Generation X

Table 9 presents the weighted mean and interpretation of the responses in the Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work survey questionnaire from the respondents who belong to Generation X.

The overall weighted mean of the Generation X respondents represents their readiness for decriminalizing the oldest profession. The total weighted mean of the Generation X responses yielded a score of thirty-five point twelve (35.12) with an interpretation of a high level of readiness. This shows that Generation X respondents are highly inclined toward accepting the policies of the proposed Senate Bill No. 2621 (Cayetano, 2015).

Table 9

	Mean Response	Interpretation
1. Prostitutes/sex workers should not be considered criminals.	3.10	Moderate
2. The people who patronize sex work should be the ones to be penalized.	3.90	High
3. Establishment owners that perpetuate sex work should be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.57	High
4. Prostitutes/sex workers should be considered victims of crime and not criminals.	3.33	Moderate
5. The person who receives sexual acts by a prostitute/sex worker should be penalized by the law.	3.65	High
6. The government should protect and support sex workers instead of being treated as criminals.	3.20	Moderate
7. People who recruit sex workers shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.86	High
8. To stop prostitution, we must stop treating sex workers as criminals.	3.17	Moderate
9. People who profit from sex work shall be penalized instead of the sex workers.	3.86	High
10. I am in favor of changing the law that criminalizes sex workers.	3.47	Moderate
TOTAL	35.12	High

Relationship of Age of Respondents to Readiness on Decriminalizing the Oldest Profession

The table shows that there is no significant relationship between the age of the respondents and their readiness to decriminalize the oldest profession.

The p-value of the coefficient table showed a value of .962. In order to accept that there is a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables, the p-value must be at 0.05 or below.

This shows that age or generation does not relate to how ready an individual is to accept the policies on decriminalizing the oldest profession.

Table 10

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	35.881	1.127		31.825	.000
	Age of Respondents	.002	.032	.003	.047	.962

a. Dependent Variable: Readiness Score

Relationship of Age of Respondents to the Social Stigma of Respondents towards the Oldest Profession

The table shows a significant relationship between the independent variable, the Age of the Respondents, and the mediating variable, the Social Stigma of the Respondents toward Sex Work.

The p-value of the coefficient table showed a value of .000. To accept a significant relationship between the independent and dependent variables; the p-value must be at 0.05 or below.

This shows that age or generation can significantly impact the social stigma towards the oldest profession of an individual.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	32.501	.948		34.296	.000
	Age of Respondents	.132	.027	.249	4.850	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Social Stigma Score

The Mediating Role of Social Stigma on The Relationship of The Generational Differences of Filipinos Towards The Readiness of Decriminalizing The Oldest Profession

This table below is a multiple regression analysis showing the relationship among the independent variable, the Age of the Respondents, the mediating variable, Social Stigma towards Sex Work, and the dependent variable, Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work.

It shows no significant relationship between the Age of Respondents and Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work, as seen in the p-value (Sig.) 0.610.

This table also shows a significant relationship between the Social Stigma Towards Sex Work and Readiness Towards Decriminalizing Sex Work, as seen in the p-value (Sig.) .026.

This shows that there is no direct relationship between Age and Generation. However, the indirect influence or the mediating role of social stigma has a significant relationship between the two variables.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	31.326	2.324		13.482	.000
	Age of Respondents	-.017	.033	-.028	-.510	.610
	Social StigmaScore	.140	.063	.122	2.238	.026

a. Dependent Variable: Readiness Score

Mediation Analysis

Table below shows the result of the Sobel test using the raw (unstandardized) coefficient (a and b) and standard error (s_a and s_b) on the regression analysis.

The table showed a p-value of 0.04, meaning the indirect influence or the mediating role of Social Stigma is significant in the relationship of Age of Respondents and Readiness toward Decriminalizing Sex Work. This result proves the findings of the multiple regression analysis conducted among all the variables, indicating that the indirect influence of social stigma towards the age of the respondents and their readiness toward decriminalizing the oldest profession is significant.

Inputs		Test Statistic	Std. Error:	p-value
a	0.132			
b	0.140	2.02303662	0.00913478	0.04306937
s_a	0.027			
s_b	0.063			

CONCLUSION

There is a high social stigma towards sex work among the respondents. However, there is a noticeable difference in the weighted mean scores among the different generations, with Generation X being the highest regarding social stigma and Generation Z being the lowest.

There is a high level of readiness toward decriminalizing sex work among the respondents. However, there is a noticeable difference in the weighted mean scores among the different generations, with Generation Z being the highest readiness and Generation X being the lowest.

The respondent's age or generation does not have a relationship with how ready they are to accept the proposal on decriminalizing sex work here in the Philippines.

The social stigma has a mediating role in the relationship between age or generational differences and the readiness to decriminalize sex work in the Philippines.

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